
PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY

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Annotation.

All activities for English vocabulary learning are based on one major reason, that is, the acknowledgement of the importance of vocabulary in language learning.

Key words.

Strategies, peculiarities, techniques, approaches.

One of the teachers' concerns in teaching English vocabulary is how to teach it in a way that learners can understand and use the vocabulary appropriately. Techniques and strategies teachers use will determine how learners learn vocabulary. Good proficiency in English cannot be achieved without having sufficient amount of vocabulary knowledge. Discussions about techniques of teaching English vocabulary have appeared in many publications, however, a widely accepted view about the best way to teach vocabulary has not been reached. For the last decade, there have been two options for teaching English vocabulary; explicit instruction and incidental learning. Explicit instruction, among others, involves discussion about new words learners need to know, breaking words into their components parts such as teaching word formation, deliberate introduction of new words, and building fluency of new words. Incidental learning refers to acquiring new words through listening, reading, speaking, or writing practice. According to Nation English vocabulary should be taught systematically because the focus of teaching is essential for learning to take place. While Hunt and Beglar on the other hand, suggest that vocabulary should be taught in a way that combines both explicit and incidental learning and the strategies for learning vocabulary should be introduced to learners.

The different approaches to teaching vocabulary has led teachers to treat vocabulary teaching differently through various kinds of classroom tasks from presentation of words in a list to involvement of learners in collaborative activities.

All activities for English vocabulary learning are based on one major reason, that is, the acknowledgement of the importance of vocabulary in language learning. Vocabulary is an “important aspect of language development”, “basic building blocks of language” and unique to language acquisition. With this recognition, learners are advised to use various strategies in order to remember and use vocabularies in communication. Many methods have been implemented in a way that can produce the most effective results and the best retention.

Unlike today, the teaching of English vocabulary in the past did not receive much attention. Moir and Nation observed that many experts assumed it was not important to teach vocabularies because learners can learn words naturally, and therefore, learning vocabularies was not emphasized. For the past decade, the interest in teaching vocabulary has been increasing and the views of teaching vocabulary has significantly changed. Therefore, researchers have shown great interests to study this vast area. A similar interest has also been shown by language teachers who strive to find out effective techniques for teaching English vocabulary.

During the history of language teaching and learning, including that of vocabulary, the methods and techniques used have been various as a result of different approaches. Obvious changes can be seen in the way language teachers asking learners to memorize a set of words through rote learning to using words in meaningfully communicative contexts. This way of teaching does not view language learning as merely a process of habit formation through repetitive Activities.

Researchers have found out that using task-based activities can improve students' vocabulary learning and their confidence. Some of task-based activities may include things such as assigning students to find out functions of words in different contexts, synonyms, antonyms, rewriting definitions, creating new sentences, or discussing the meaning of the same word in different sentences.

In order to help learners acquire new English words, they need to be taught strategies for learning vocabulary. Graves suggests that learners need to learn about words not simply acquire them. Direct teaching of vocabulary learning strategies such as use of dictionaries, use of context clues, or identifying parts of words can help learners to become more independent learners.

It is important to note that the emergence of new technologies has provided ELT with effective means and options of teaching language including vocabulary. Therefore, it is justifiable to suggest that multimedia software be utilized in language teaching. As pointed out by Yang and Chen learners will experience the

joy of language learning if learning is facilitated with technology such as use of mobile phone, computer, or access to the internet. According to Chen & Chung many researchers believe that electronic devices such as mobile phones can support both formal and informal learning and it is an important issue in English language education especially in EFL contexts.

Numerous studies on English vocabulary learning strategies have been conducted. To mention a few, are studies conducted by Tsai & Chang, Loucky, Dolati & Mikael, and Taki & Khazaeni. Those studies, and others, have focused on learner strategies of learning vocabulary, effects of using dictionaries on vocabulary acquisition, effects of using games to facilitate students' vocabulary learning, or using cell phones or other mobile devices for teaching or learning vocabulary. In spite of new insights into teaching vocabulary and useful information from the various research, the contexts and settings of the studies have been confined to classroom experiments or cross sectional research.

Design of the Study

This study employed a quasi-experimental pre test - post test experimental design to investigate the effectiveness of using seven teaching strategies to improve students' vocabulary acquisition. The strategies are context drill, word-on-board game, flash-card game, mini-presentations, role playing, dictionary consultation, and blended learning.

Sample of the Study

The sample of the study consisted of 248 first-year students studying within the Faculty of Education of the University of Dammam. The sample was tested after the use of the traditional deductive method and was divided into two groups, the control group and the experimental group. The two groups were composed of randomly selected students who were studying English as a basic requirement of the Faculty of Education and the Deanship of the Preparatory Year. The data collection was completed during the first semester of the academic year 2013/2014. The students' ages ranged from 19 to 22 years.

Instrument of the Study and Method

A vocabulary pre and post test was applied before and after the implementation of each teaching method on the same groups of students. For example, if teacher A used role playing to teach vocabulary she would test the students before and after using this method. With every method there was a test for students' undergrading. One of the researchers on the University of Dammam campuses met with the five EFL teachers and discussed the research idea and the

main research question, which deals with the most effective method to teach vocabulary. Each teacher was teaching 30 to 35 students and one was teaching two sections. Each teacher initially taught vocabulary using the didactic method and then taught using the methods identified below. The teacher applied pre and post tests to the group and the results were documented and subsequently analysed by the researcher.

Participants

The number of female students enrolled in the preparatory year within the Faculty of Education and the Deanship of the Preparatory Year at the University of Dammam in the fall of 2014 was 2,242 (with females comprising 60% of the total) students for the university's branch program used in this research which encompasses the health, education, science, engineering, administrative (business), and computer sciences., The age range of the participants was 18 to 22 (the majority of whom were between 18 and 20 with an Arabic language background). Because of the gender segregation in Saudi Arabia and hence our greater access to the female student population, the participants in this study were exclusively female. Thus, gender is not a variable that was considered in the research design. Further, in order to minimize the impact of external factors that may affect the findings, such as the ability to speak multiple languages, only those students who were working with a first language L1 of Arabic were included in the analysis.

In this study seven methods were employed to teach vocabulary to students in their preparatory year. In the quotations set out below, the teachers shed light on the methods that they used to teach the students. For instance, according to teacher A, the context drill

...uses vocab in context (groups): put all unit words on the board and students have to make a skit, conversation, paragraph, or short story using the words in a context related to the unit-usually I will ask them to use half of the words; however, for differentiated learning-the strong groups I will ask to use all of the words-the weaker groups, less of the words-this only works if the instructor has assigned the groups. I also usually incorporate a grammar point here as well (Teacher A).

Another teacher explained her use of the word-on-board game, which she defined as follows:

Game daily review (teams)-one student is a judge; one student from each team comes to the board-the teachers say a definition and then they write the word on the board aided by their team with the correct spelling-the first team to get it wins the point (Teacher B).

A third teacher who used the flash-card game explained it as follows:

My students do a vocabulary workbook over the semester which amounts to 100 new words from their reading book lessons. In the workbook they must include five elements: the English word, the word in Arabic, its part of speech, the definition and an example of the word in a sentence or a drawing or an example. There are 10 lessons for the semester and 10 vocabulary words per unit. I go over the words in class and have them give definitions or sentences to show understanding. We have a vocabulary test each week, but it is combined with a reading test or a listening test, so I can't give you the numbers for these tests. For the review of the words, we play games before the exam to help them review. Ninety percent of the girls do very well on the vocabulary sections of the test, scoring from 90 percent to 100. Those girls who don't study or do their workbook get in the 70s or less, but this does not occur too often.

Teacher E explained mini-presentations as follows:

Every week each student brings a term or a vocabulary that they heard on TV or read in a newspaper. She will then bring it to class to discuss it and explain it to the group. In each session every student will have 7-10 minutes to do a mini presentation about the term she studied. This will be repeated for 12 weeks. So if I have 30 students in classroom this means that the class will be exposed to over 12 times 30 words per semester. I found this to be very productive METHOD.

As one of the professors suggested, it is valuable to have each student use role playing to animate the vocabulary being studied, an approach that adds fun and excitement to the teaching and learning atmosphere and thus helps to arouse the interest of the learners and make the language acquisition process more effective. Dictionary consultation is another method that was employed. As one of the professors explained regarding her instructions to her students.

Use your dictionary (groups): (a) Write the new words on the board. Go over about half of the known ones together as a class usually through definitions, pronunciation, parts of speech, synonyms. (b) The other half of the students look up in their dictionaries, have group roles and the reporter shares with the entire class. I've given them websites for ESL learners and they also know I discourage Google translate as often it is incorrect and I want them to use English synonyms if possible as they are at an advanced LEVEL.

Blended learning was said to imply the following:

Students will learn to use computer databases and online sources in English as well as library materials and will significantly sharpen their ability to read journal

papers in English. The course will emphasize critical reading, thinking, and understanding in the context of comprehensive research projects. Beginners will be introduced to the nature and uses of online learning tools. Students will learn to read and understand English vocabulary. The students will collect different uses of the same and that reflect their interests and experience. Students will also learn to read their work and the work of their peers as other readers will make revisions in response to the peer evaluations.

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